

MACHIAVELLI'S CRITIQUE OF POLITICAL PRACTICE OF RENAISSANCE HUMANISM

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Abstract: This article aims to address the context in which Machiavelli, who was part of the set of humanist thinkers, on the other hand, also disagreed with the political ideas of his contemporaries, also launched a strong critique of the political practice of Christianity, recognizing its weakness and inadequacy of the social ends necessary for a society to strengthen and prosper. The starting point of the humanist authors was the ideal of freedom, which, taken in its traditional sense, meant independence and republican self-government. To these thinkers the good ruler should have prudence, temperance, honesty and not merely appear to possess these virtues. Facing humanist ideals, Machiavelli formulated his political precepts, opposing the conceptions presented, because the policy for this Florentine has its own rules. To analyze these themes the Florentine had to contradict a whole universe of political ideals, among them those of Christianity itself, responsible for the moral conception of his time. Machiavelli directed his attacks on Christian ingenuity in politics, claiming that Christianity forms weak and unprepared men for public life. Christian political practice did not favor the ideal of the common good, for its purpose was not to exalt the fatherland but to hope in eternal life, rendering men detached from the things of this world.

Keywords: Machiavelli; Political practice; Humanists; Christianity; Criticism.

A CRÍTICA DE MAQUIAVEL À PRÁTICA POLÍTICA DO HUMANISMO RENASCENTISTA

Resumo: O presente artigo tem o objetivo de abordar o contexto no qual Maquiavel, que fazia parte do conjunto dos pensadores humanistas, por outro lado, também discordava das ideias políticas de seus contemporâneos, também lançou forte crítica à prática política do cristianismo, reconhecendo sua fraqueza e inadequação quanto aos fins sociais necessários para que uma sociedade se fortaleça e prospere. O ponto de partida dos autores humanistas era o ideal de liberdade, que, tomado em seu sentido tradicional, significava independência e autogoverno republicano. Para esses pensadores o bom governante deveria ter prudência, temperança, honestidade e não apenas aparentar a posse dessas virtudes. Diante dos ideais humanistas, Maquiavel formulou seus preceitos políticos, opondo-se às concepções apresentadas, pois a política para esse florentino, possui suas próprias regras. Para analisar esses temas o florentino precisou contrariar todo um universo de ideais políticas, dentre elas, as do próprio cristianismo, responsável pela concepção de moral da sua época. Maquiavel direcionou seus ataques à ingenuidade cristã na política, afirmando que o cristianismo forma homens fracos e despreparados para a vida pública. A prática política cristã não favorecia o ideal do bem comum, pois sua finalidade não consistia na exaltação da pátria, mas na esperança na vida eterna, tornando os homens desapegados às coisas deste mundo.

Palavras-chave: Maquiavel; Prática política; Humanistas; Cristianismo; Crítica.

THE CRITIQUE OF MACHIAVELLI TO HUMANISTS

Machiavelli, a contemporary of the sixteenth century, participated in an essentially humanistic culture in which rhetoric occupied a place of great importance. A man of letters, he knew the literary genres and traditional rules to which every work, no matter how innovative, should be subjected.

In the formal sense, there is no innovation in Machiavelli's works, as they belong to well-known literary genres, widespread and consolidated in late-fifteenth-century political thought. However, regarding the treatment of the themes, it is clear that the Florentine subverts the lessons that the tradition has consecrated.

In the *Prince*, one can see Machiavelli's attack on the political theories of his contemporaries. At first, the Florentine criticizes current theories for failing to emphasize the importance of brute force in political life. For Machiavelli's contemporary humanists, if the prince had a virtuous life, he would be able to achieve the supreme goals of honor, glory, and fame. Machiavelli considers this perspective naive, since it does not take into account that the maintenance of a successful government depends on a willingness to resort to effective military force. However, it would be a mistake to consider that Machiavelli was the first to introduce this idea into the field of humanist political thinking, since the willingness to fight for the homeland, the possibility of using violence to defend it, has always been affirmed by Machiavelli's predecessor humanists. , as an indispensable element of the authentic citizen.

There is no doubt about the claim that Machiavelli attaches great importance to brute force in the administration of a government. In the *Prince*, there are three chapters devoted to the analysis of military affairs, stating that the main foundations of every state consist of "good laws and good weapons" and "having good weapons, inevitably there will be good laws." It also discusses a subject that has always been of interest to humanists of the early fifteenth century, namely the folly and the dangers of resorting to mercenary troops. It

proposes, as a rule, that if a prince bases his state's defense on mercenaries, he will never achieve stability or security. The solution proposed by the Florentine, reminding us of the humanist spirit, is that every prince must strive for the constitution of a militia of citizens, who must also command in person.

One point that Machiavelli disputes about the prevailing theses among humanist authors refers to the role of *virtú* in political life. There were two central ideas about *virtu* that emerged from the humanist tradition of moral and political thinking. The first was that *virtu* is the quality that enables a prince to accomplish his noblest ends; The second era is that the possession of virtue can be identified with the possession of all the main virtues. As a result, a common advice prevailed among humanist writers, that if a ruler wished to maintain his state and achieve the goals of honor, glory, and fame, he should above all cultivate the fullest set of Christian virtues. And it is precisely this conclusion that Machiavelli rejects¹.

The Florentine agrees that the proper goals for a prince are honor, glory and fame. But it rejects the prevailing conviction that the safest way to accomplish these ends will always be to act conventionally virtuous.

Machiavelli sometimes presents himself with some obscurity, for it leads us to understand that if princes have an obligation to rule their deeds by virtue, they must, however, realize that in order to act as virtuously as possible, they must give up. of the pretense of acting always virtuously. There is sometimes irony in Machiavelli's expositions to be cruel just to be kind. ²

In dealing with the virtue of liberality, the Florentine states that the desire to appear generous leads princes to impose unnecessary taxation upon their people, a ruler who is not afraid to act sparingly may find that in due course he must be recognized as liberal. ³

As for the virtue of clemency, Machiavelli wrote that Caesar Borgia was considered cruel, but adds that this cruelty raised the Romany, uniting it and returning order and obedience. A ruler who is strong enough, "setting an

¹ SKINNER, Quentin. **The Foundations of Modern Political Thought**. p. 151

² Ibidem, p. 152

³ MAQUIAVEL. **The Prince**. p. 101

example or two" in due course "will prove more compassionate" than a prince who fails to suppress "the disorders that lead to murder and prey" just so as not to be called of cruel⁴.

Regarding the role that conventional virtues can play in obtaining the honor, glory, and fame desired by princes, Machiavelli states that nothing is as important as keeping up appearances. The prince's goal is to "be considered an honorable person" and earn universal praise. The prince does not necessarily have to have all the good qualities, but he certainly must appear to possess them under all circumstances⁵.

The reason why Machiavelli attaches importance to dissimulation lies in the second moment of his criticism of the humanist tradition about the role of virtues in political life. The Florentine argues that it is important for princes to appear to be virtuous in the conventional way, but it often becomes impossible for them to behave in a conventionally virtuous manner. The reason he proposes for this fact is that the prince "will realize that some of the things that appear to be virtues will, if he practices them, ruin him, while some of the things that seem vicious will give him security and prosperity".⁶

In the fifteenth chapter of the Prince, in discussing "Why men, and especially princes, are praised or insulted" Machiavelli expounds his most singular thesis. At first it states the conclusion it intends to demonstrate, namely, "the gulf between how one lives and the way one should live is so vast that one who disdains what one actually does, to worry about what one should do, learn the way of its ruin rather than its conservation"⁷.

To illustrate his thesis, he launches an attack against the virtues that the humanist authors presented as the most suitable for the rulers to cultivate. Machiavelli continues to employ all humanistic conventions when he expounds his own doctrine of supposed princely virtues. He points out that there is always talk about men and especially princes, exposing the various qualities that bring

⁴ Ibidem, p. 103

⁵ Ibidem, p. 108

⁶ Ibidem, p. 100

⁷ Ibidem, p. 99

them praise or rejection. The Florentine focuses on the three princely virtues that have always received the most prominence in such discourses: liberality, mercy, and loyalty.

After establishing the princely virtues, Machiavelli begins to demolish them one by one. The first virtue he analyzes is liberality, stating to the prince that "if your actions are influenced by your desire to have a reputation as a liberal, you will have many problems." The second is clemency, showing that in Scipio's case she turned out to be a fatal trait, which would even have tarnished his fame and glory had the Roman senate not restrained him in time. Finally, he discusses the virtue of faith in the word given, concluding that a prince who follows this obligation will discover on many occasions that it puts him in a disadvantageous position.⁸

Machiavelli also insists that if a prince wishes to maintain his state, he will often realize how essential and positively advantageous it is to use those vices that humanistic writers advised princes to avoid at all costs. Beginning with greed, he states that it is inevitable if the prince intends to keep his subjects united and loyal. Finally, he underscores the value of deception and deception, insisting that

"the experience of our day shows that the princes who performed the greatest deeds were those who spoke lightly, who were able to deceive by cunning, and who, after all, triumphed over those who were guided by the principles of honesty".

Machiavelli is in complete agreement with the more traditional authors as to the goals that princes should aim for. As he himself states, the objective of the ruler should be to maintain his state and accomplish great deeds and thus aspire to honor, glory and fame. The difference between Machiavelli and his contemporaries lies in the nature of the methods he deems appropriate to

⁸ MAQUIAVEL. *The Prince*. p. 108

accomplish his ends. The starting point of the humanist writers of the day was that for the prince to achieve such goals, he must be certain to follow the norms of Christian morality under any circumstances.

Machiavelli, on the other hand, starts from the idea that if a prince acts virtuously in every case, he will soon discover how much "he must suffer among so many who are not virtuous." The fundamental criticism that the Florentine addresses to the thinkers of his time concerns the fact that they do not understand what they think defines the dilemma that characterizes the prince.

According to the Florentine, these authors want to have the right to express their admiration for a great driver of men as was Hannibal⁹. But at the same time they intend to condemn what made their exploits possible, especially the inhuman cruelty in which Machiavelli sees the key to Hannibal's success and glory. The way out of the Florentine is to accept unreservedly that if a prince is serious about maintaining his state, he will have to give up the demands of Christian virtue.

Therefore, the difference between Machiavelli and his contemporaries cannot be correctly assessed as the difference between a moral view of politics and a conception of politics that would be divorced from morality. The difference lies in two distinct moralities, which ultimately must be done. This theme, which in the next chapter will be exposed with breadth.

⁹ Hannibal (247 BC-183 BC) was a Carthaginian general and prominent tactical and military leader, and was known for his performance in the second Punic war against the Roman Republic, but was defeated.

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